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Система Работ Над Глагольными Синонимами

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Annotation: *In this article, we propose a system of work on verbal synonyms in the national University. One of the most difficult questions on the topic of "Verb" is the use of verb types. The proposed exercises are aimed both at mastering the grammatical category of the verb type, and at determining and actively using verbal synonymy in speech.*

Keywords: *Verb synonymy, semantic structure of the verb, grammatical category, use of verb types, imperfect and perfect forms.*

When teaching Russian to students of national groups of non-linguistic faculties, it is necessary to take into account the specialization of the university where they study. Russian Russian is the task of a non-linguistic university teacher to teach students to actively use the Russian language within the university curriculum and prepare them for independent work with Russian scientific and technical text. In our opinion, synonymy is an aspect in teaching students special vocabulary. The task of the teacher is to teach them not only to understand synonymous structures when reading texts, but also to freely and quickly perceive them by ear. In recent years, separate works have appeared, which provide methodological recommendations for the assimilation of synonyms by students and students of Russian groups, and a system of exercises for the study of lexical synonymy has been developed. However, the methodology for studying synonymy at the national university has not been sufficiently developed. There are no major studies on the study of synonymy in relation to a national audience. Our choice of only verbal synonymy is rejoiced by the fact that "the semantic structure of the verb is more capacious and flexible than all other grammatical categories. The sequence of work on verbs, the connection between sections, the amount of program material, techniques and means of studying it are determined by the tasks of studying this part of speech, its linguistic features and cognitive capabilities. The main tasks are to form the initial concept of the verb as a part of speech, to develop the ability to consciously use the verb in oral and written statements, to increase the level of mental development of students, to develop the skill of spelling the personal endings of the most commonly used verbs I and II conjugation. All tasks are solved in interconnection. The linguistic features of the

verb are quite complex, so students are introduced only to some categories specific to this part of speech. When selecting the material, the degree of its necessity for the conscious solution of speech and spelling problems is taken into account. Students observe the use of verbs in speech that answer the questions what to do? And what should I do? They learn to put the question to the word correctly. It is important to teach how to distinguish the type of verb with the help of questions, since without this it is impossible to study the change of verbs at times. The system of work on verbal synonyms at the national university is being built in the sequence provided for by the Russian language program when studying the verb. Exercises can be grouped into sections of the topic "Verb" and performed at all stages of development. One of the difficult questions on the topic of "Verb" is the use of verb types. The proposed exercises are aimed both at mastering the grammatical category of the verb type, and at defining and actively using verbal synonymy in speech. We introduce students to the topic "Synonyms". Synonyms are words that are close or identical in meaning, naming the same concept in different ways: destroy, eliminate, eradicate, abolish. Several synonymous words form a synonymous series. The members of the synonymous series have a common semantic basis. For example, the synonymous series order- command – command -directive- prescription has the general meaning of "an instruction to do something." Usually this general meaning is expressed by the main word of the synonymous series – its dominant. (The dominant of the above synonymous series is the word command). Other members of the synonymous series, in addition to the common meaning for all, express additional lexical and stylistic shades: lexical proper (catastrophe- collapse), gradation (big - huge - huge), shades of emotional and expressive coloring (run away - run away - run away), etc.

Types of synonyms Synonyms are divided into two large groups: absolute and partial. The latter, in turn, are classified into several subtypes. Auxiliary synonyms are distinguished in a separate form, which in themselves are not such, but become so under certain conditions. • Absolute (doublets) Absolute synonyms are words that have exactly the same meaning. They are interchangeable without violating the meaning of the sentence. They are less common than partial ones. Example: car — car, boundless — boundless, huge — huge. Doublets are more often nouns. In the modern language, their number is falling due to a change in stylistic coloring and the loss of the initial meaning. For example, the term "linguistics" has been forgotten, it has been replaced by "linguistics". Or the words "goalkeeper" and "goalkeeper". At one time they were completely interchangeable, but gradually the first word passed into the category of stylistic substitutions. • Partial Partial synonyms are words that have a similar meaning, but are not completely identical in meaning. If you replace a word with a partial analogue, the sentence will change slightly. Example: wet — damp, storm — hurricane, mother — parent. Several types of synonyms are partial:

- Semantic. They indicate a different degree of manifestation of the same sign. They manifest themselves in a certain context: adult — adult;
- Stylistic. They differ in stylistic shades. They can relate to different historical epochs, be used in different spheres (national and slang), and differ in origin (Russian and foreign). This includes euphemisms; lavatory — toilet;
- Semantic and stylistic. They differ in shades of meaning and stylistic coloring: go — trudge. Absolute and partial synonyms are called authentic or synonyms of the language. They have developed historically, are stable and have existed for a long time. Along with them, there are speech synonyms in the vocabulary that converge in meaning only in certain cases.
- Contextual Contextual synonyms usually do not replace each other, but become identical at the author's request in a certain context. They belong to speech or temporary lexical units. Example: I

knocked a samovar on the table (here I "knocked" in the meaning I put it). Contextual synonyms do not maintain stable synonymous relationships, any words from different parts of speech can act in their role. The use of synonyms makes our speech more accurate, vivid, expressive, emotional and beautiful. Synonyms connect parts of the text and allow you to avoid unjustified repetitions of the same word, thereby avoiding speech errors. The existence of synonyms allows us to convey a thought to writers, poets, journalists to express a thought, convey a feeling, name a particular phenomenon more clearly. Synonyms help explain the meaning of unknown words. Thus, synonyms are understood to mean words that are different in sound, but the same or similar in lexical meaning. Synonyms differ in the shade of their meaning, their use in different styles of speech, the scope of use and the degree of modernity. Synonyms play a big role in the Russian language, in oral and written speech.

Phraseological Synonyms-phraseological units are partial, but they stand out in a separate subspecies due to their unusual nature - not only words are interchangeable here, but also phrases (phraseological units), stable expressions. Example: a little — a cat cried a lot, like a cat with a dog — I can't stand it. The units of this group are heterogeneous, and when using them, it is important to take into account relevance in context, grammatical compatibility. There are common, official, colloquial, colloquial or abusive, outdated and modern, professional and slang. Therefore, the correct application is very important. Synonymous series Several synonyms united by a common meaning form a synonymous series. The words in the list are related, the main or dominant is always in the first place, which sets the character of the series. The core word is a word with a neutral coloring, the most common one, which conveys only the main meaning. There are stylistic or semantic nuances in other terms of the series. Example: red — crimson — scarlet — poppy — crimson — carmine. The number of lexical units in the synonymic series is different. In one case, there are two or three terms, in the other there are more than a dozen words, stable expressions and phraseological units. It is not always easy to recognize them. For example, it is difficult to determine the difference between a cliff and a rock, comical and funny. To facilitate the task, the selection of units in a synonymous series is carried out by comparing with the main word. The task of the preparatory exercises that we offer is aimed at mastering linguistic material - semantics, grammatical forms of synonymous verbs, accumulation of students' vocabulary

Exercise.1. In these sentences, underline the verbs, Choose synonyms for them. Determine the type of verb.

1. The red wings of the sunset go out. The wattles are quietly dozing in the fog. (S.Yesenin).
2. Cabbies drive, the glass in the windows shudders from the knock of their carriages and carts (M. Gorky).

Exercise.2. Write it down, choosing from the data in parentheses the synonyms that are most appropriate in meaning. Explain the meanings of the type of verbs.

1. Sometimes Pavel. (Wrote out, wrote out) something from books on a separate piece of paper and also (hid, hid) it.
2. On holidays (left, left) in the morning, (returned, returned) late at night. (S.Ilyenko)

Exercise 3. Form perfect verbs from these imperfect verbs and emphasize alternating consonants in each synonymous pair of verbs.

Run Away- Treat -... Captivate- Decorate- ... Please- Light Up- ...

Exercise 4. Replace these verbs with synonymous ones. Determine the way the species is formed: in which cases the species pairs are grammatical forms of the same word and in which cases they are different words.

Overcome, choose, say, accept, protect, manifest, spend, disappear, and shrink.

Exercise 5. Insert one of the verbs instead of dots. Underline the alternating vowels in each synonymous pair of verbs.

1. When friction occurs, a certain amount of heat is possible. The earth receives a huge amount of heat and light from the sun every day (receive, receive).
2. A scientist... an important problem. He is of course (to decide to decide)

Exercise 6. From these verbs, make up synonymous rows, Highlight the dominants. Determine the type of verbs. Exhaust, multiply, publish, protect, guard, publish use (to the end,) print, save, protect, and exhaust release.

Exercise 7. Replace the underlined verbs in these sentences, without changing the meaning, with verbs of a different type. Identify the differences in the formation of species pairs.

1. Dawn was just breaking through, and the fields glowed bluishly between the black copses. (Nikolaev).
2. Large-winged owls called out from between noiselessly, unexpectedly, and the horse snorted, shied away.(I. Bunin)

Exercise 8. Explain how the above synonymous series were formed. Determine the type of verbs.

To find out, to scout, to pull out, to pull out, to inquire, to get to the bottom of it.

Exercise 9. Arrange the synonyms in ascending order of the attribute. Explain the meaning of the perfect and imperfect verbs.

To be afraid, to be afraid, to tremble, to tremble, to be afraid, to be afraid, to be afraid, to be timid.

Exercise 10. Determine the differences of verbal synonyms within the same synonymic series (shade of meaning, usage, morpheme composition, type): master, overcome, defeat, overcome, break, break, crush, and destroy.

Exercise 11. Combine these synonymous verbs with one of the nouns.Explain the way the verb type is formed.

To help, to facilitate, to facilitate (progress to the underachieving, neighbor, success). To have, possess, possess (property, language, skill).

Exercise 12. Choose synonyms for these words. Make sentences with words of the same synonymous series.

To win, to laugh, to be silent, to study, to fix, to match, to observe, to unite.

Exercise 13.With each member of these series of synonyms, form such phrases that would reveal the shades of their meanings.

1. Lean over, bend over, lean over
2. Numb, stupefy, petrify, ossify, stiffen, freeze, freeze, stiffen.

Exercise 14. Form acceptable combinations of each word (from parentheses) with synonyms of the corresponding row. In each case, highlight the phrases that seem to you the most successful, and make sentences with them. Disappear, disappear, melt, evaporate (values, goods, money, talents, criminal, hope, desire, patience.)

The performance of preparatory exercises expands students' understanding of the possibilities of using Russian verbs. The proposed exercises on verbal synonymy do not pretend to be complete and solve the problem of studying the types of the verb. However, the results of testing these exercises in foreign language groups of the university had a positive effect.

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